

#7

Evaluation & Impact Assessment
‘HOT TOPICS’: COALESCING INTERESTS ACROSS BOUNDARIES

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Project proposal stages; and all stages when diverse forms of knowledge are combined, and when actors/stakeholders must interrogate/internalise new forms of knowledge.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1.5-3 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. Can be conducted physically with participants in a room or on an online platform such as Klaxoon, Pinup, or Mural. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool # 13.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify 'Hot Topics' of interest to partners across disciplinary boundaries.
- Add the diverse knowledges/perspectives of the different partners to each of the hot topics
- Combine the knowledges/perspectives of actors, by creating a 'story' (or narrative) about how these knowledges interrelate and intertwine
- Create a matrix for external stakeholders to assess 'insider' knowledges/perspectives (in a multi-actor consortium) for thoroughness.
- Continuously evaluate how the different knowledges/perspectives of different partners (and stakeholders) inform project activities and outputs.
- Adapt how knowledges/perspectives creatively combine in response to a challenge/activity, availing of new knowledges/perspectives as they are developed.

Background and Logic

The aim of multi-actor projects/initiatives (required for interactive innovation) is that they combine different knowledges. By definition, they aim to be transdisciplinary – which requires that knowledges are blended to create knowledge that goes beyond the sum of all the individual knowledges. Transdisciplinary (multi-actor) projects aim to go beyond approaches that layer knowledges on each other (inter- & multi-disciplinarity) to fuel innovation. It is the creative combination of knowledges that fuels innovation.

Deliberate strategies must be employed to assist actors to creatively combine their knowledges, much like a jigsaw puzzle (that has no instructions or guide, but is continuously evolving!). 'Hot Topics', originally used by the European Network of Rural Development (ENRD) to facilitate members of multi-actor groups to work together, can be used to coalesce different actors' knowledges/perspectives around topics of common interest.

This tool identifies the latest hot-topics (across disciplinary/professional boundaries) in relation to a particular theme, and different actors express their unique knowledges/perspectives in relation to the topics. The knowledges/perspectives are creatively combined using a story-board format. The tool uses a matrix to appraise internal partners' knowledge/perspectives for thoroughness. Together, the storyboard and matrix provide a tool for periodic evaluation of how well project activities are incorporating transdisciplinary (blended) knowledge to project/initiative activities. Transdisciplinary knowledge is also periodically updated as new knowledge is produced.

Materials

- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Online storyboard generator or template (simple comic strip template) printed (large size) for hand written/drawn entries.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.

Step 2: Identification of Project Themes

- Facilitate participants to identify the main themes/topics of the project/initiative, with reference to a project contract, if one is in place. The facilitator or participants write/s these on post-its, placed on flip-chart paper.
- Some project partners are likely to have led the formation of the project/initiative and others are likely to have been invited 'on board'. Thus, there will be varying levels of awareness and knowledge of the themes/topics. The facilitator must be actively aware of this and ensure that there is adequate time devoted to questions/exploration of the main themes/topics.
- Where there are many themes/topics, ask participants 'do any of these go together and why?' (to cluster the theme/topics into manageable, distinctive themes).
- The output from step two is a list of themes/topics relevant to the project/initiative. Each theme/topic should be placed on the top of its own dedicated sheet of flipchart paper (currently blank)

Step 3: Adding Knowledges/ Perspectives to Themes & Identification of 'Hot-Topics'

- Take each theme in turn, and ask participants what their perspectives are in relation to the theme (examples might be antimicrobial resistance, or short food supply chains). Ask participants the following types of probing questions:
 - » What is your experience of this [theme name]? This is an important exercise in facilitating partners to understand each other's different experiences and forms of experience.
 - » What do you/other people in the sector think are the main strategies to deal with this? What are the main approaches, or what advice would you give to others/clients?
 - » What are the 'hot topics' (i.e. main points of interest/strategy/areas of action) from your perspectives?
 - » Ask participants to write their hot topics on post-its and place them on the flip-chart sheet, entitled with the name of the theme/topic.
- After each theme has been brainstormed (identifying hot topics), revisit the title of each theme. The facilitator asks: 'considering the range of knowledges/perspectives identified under this theme, do you wish to re-name it? It may be the case that partners may not wish to change the title, which is an endorsement of the existing title.
- The output from Step 3 is deciding the title of the themes and hot topics in relation to the theme that have been brainstormed from the perspectives of all the different partners in the multi-actor project/initiative.

Example from the SKIN Horizon 2020 Consortium: themes (products, organisational/institutional/systems, governance, sales) and associated hot topics (interactive version accessible at: [D2.1](#))

Example from SWAB
(consortium funded by the Research Stimulus Fund of Ireland's Department of Agriculture Food and the Marine)

Step 4: Blending Knowledges Through Co-Creation of Storyboards

- For each theme, facilitate participants to develop a storyboard, by prompting the following/asking participants the following types of questions:
 - » We have several different types of people around the table, all with different types of perspectives/knowledges in relation to this topic.
 - » Lots of hot topics have been identified
 - » Can you imagine, in a story, where people similar to you working in a real life context might come together to work on this theme, addressing the hot topics you have identified?
 - » Remember, a story has a beginning, middle and end, with plenty of twists and turns!
 - » I'll assign each of you to a character. For example, the partner in the room who is a farmer is assigned to a farmer character. However, the character in the story has a different name to the partner him or herself, which gives more freedom in constructing the story.
 - » Once all characters are assigned, we'll go to the first scene of the story. What happens first? Which of you can think of a scene? What problem is the starting point? What happens next? Which character appears in the scene? Does anyone come into the scene next? What might a character like him/her say, consider his/her profession or discipline?

What challenges emerge? What solutions might be available? Who is needed for that? What resources/people are missing? Etc.

- » The output from Step 4 is a co-created storyboard, which blends the knowledges/perspectives/hot topics of diverse partners into a single interactive story. The co-created storyboard pinpoints where knowledge blends (and also diverges) The storyboard can optionally be co-created virtually (or on a screen) using storyboard software (such as Boords, pictured below), a pre-printed template, or indeed flipchart paper. If a printed template/flipchart paper is used, it is advisable to have a collection of random images that people can select to use to accompany the brief story text (such images are available in online storyboarding tools).

Excerpt from example storyboard from the Ploutos (Horizon 2020) project. Full version available [here](#):

4

A marketing consultant, Michelle, is approached by Anita. Michelle asks Anita about her marketing approach. She asks, who is the customer (across the value chain), and how Anita manages to convey the values of her product to the end consumer? Does she have certification regarding sustainability & animal welfare standards? How well is this certification conveyed to the consumer? Michelle values change - she supports and seeks to activate changes in consumer demands ...

5

Anita explains to Michelle problems when it comes to implementing new technology on her farm. ... For cultural reasons... and maybe due to lack of knowledge of how to use the technology... Technology is a way of capturing information for the consumer, and is often important for conveying messages to the consumer. In a context where Anita feels that she's not getting rewarded price-wise - there is technology to better capture the measurement of high welfare standards. This technology is essential in collating information and presenting it to the consumer. ... One of the challenges is that she feels, based on past experience, that she won't get rewarded for it. ... This is a conflict

6

Patrick, a local innovation broker, would like to see improvement where Anita's situation is concerned. He would like to help through programmes & tools, such as innovation programmes, knowledge transfer & exchange initiatives through, for example, the National Rural Networks & through access to databases of projects that help in this area. He focuses on the importance of bringing people together to identify ways for consumers to access products with high welfare and sustainability attributes.

Step 5: Validation & Widening of Knowledges/Perspectives with Stakeholders

- Where the multi-actor consortium meets with wider stakeholders and wish to add to the hot topics (knowledges/perspectives already brainstormed (internally) for each theme), a matrix can be used to validate/widen/enrich the knowledges/perspectives with those of stakeholders.
- The facilitator prepares a 'matrix' on a white-board or flipchart. The matrix consists simply of a list of the themes, presented on the upper horizontal row.
- In the same way that partners were invited in Step 3, invite stakeholders to add their 'hot-topics' (as well as elucidating their knowledges/perspectives/experiences), writing them on post-its (with scribes assisting where necessary). The post-its are placed underneath themes to form columns.
- At a subsequent meeting (involving partners) facilitate a discussion on if/how stakeholders' compare with internally identified hot topics; and if/how project hot topics should be adapted.
- This step can be implemented regularly, when interacting with new groups of stakeholders.

Step 6: Assessment of Project Activities and Updating of Transdisciplinary (Multi-actor) Knowledge

- At project meetings in relation to project activities:
 - » Revisit the hot-topics – are they being addressed and are some being addressed more than others? What actions can be taken to improve how hot-topics are more comprehensively addressed?
 - » Revisit the storyboards – are opportunities for interplays and exchanges of knowledges (as depicted in the storyboards) being exploited? What actions can be taken to improve opportunities?
 - » Optionally, create new storyboards, that incorporate wider hot-topics and more opportunities for interplays and exchanges of knowledges. At the end of the project, a suite of storyboards will have been created, evidencing a rigorous, reflexive transdisciplinary (multi-actor) approach.

